

THE ERESIDAE OF SOUTH AFRICA

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ABSTRACT

The family Eresidae is known from nine genera and 98 species. Five genera and 30 species are known from South Africa and they are all listed on the World Spider Catalog (2020). Three genera *Paradonea* (Miller et al., 2012), *Seothyra* (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1990) and *Stegodyphus* (Kraus & Kraus, 1988) have been revised. Of the 11 *Dresserus* species nine are Data Deficient, known only from one sex or under sampled. Only two species, *D. colsoni* Tucker, 1920 and *D. kannemeyeri* Tucker, 1920 have a wide distribution and are of Least Concern. The three *Gandanameno* species have a wide distribution and are also of Least Concern. Of the five *Paradonea* species only *P. splendens* (Lawrence, 1936) is Data Deficient, the other four species have a wide distribution. Five species of *Seothyra* are known from the region and two of them *S. perelegans* Simon, 1906 and *S. semicoccinea* Simon, 1906 are known only from one sex and therefore Data Deficient. The six *Stegodyphus* species all have a wide distribution.

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FAMILY ERESIDAE C. L. Koch, 1845

The family Eresidae C.L. Koch, 1845 is known from nine genera and 98 species (World Spider Catalog 2020). Five genera and 30 species are known from South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: Velvet spiders.

MORPHOLOGY: Body size: 7-20 mm (male smaller, sexual dimorphism in size, shape and colour). Colour: various hues of dark-brown, yellowish brown to grey, abdomen sometimes with distinct patterns formed by white, orange or red setae. Carapace rectangular; high or slightly flattened; usually thickly clothed with setae; fovea circular but variable in depth; eyes 8, median eyes close together; with lateral eyes wide apart; posterior lateral eyes usually positioned far back on the carapace. Abdomen rounded to oval; thickly clothed with setae; frequently with patterns. Legs short and stout; thickly clothed with setae; tarsi are usually united to metatarsi, almost rigid joints.

LIFE STYLE: Webs are diverse and differ between genera, usually a sheet-like signal-web radiating from a retreat made of cribellate silk; the shape of retreat varies between genera.

TAXONOMY: The genera *Paradonea* (Miller et al., 2012), *Seothyra* (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1990) and *Stegodyphus* (Kraus & Kraus, 1988) have been revised.

Eresidae. Eresinae. a: *Gandanameno* sp., dorsal view; b: chelicera, ventral view, showing strong chitinous keel; c: *Dresserus* sp., spinnerets in ventral view, showing 4-partite cribellum; d: *Gandanameno* sp., spinnerets in ventral view, showing 2-partite cribellum; e: male palp, lateral view; f: epigyne. (after Dippenaar-Schoeman & Jocqué 1997)

GENUS *DRESSERUS* Simon, 1876

The genus *Dresserus* represented by 24 African endemic species (World Spider Catalog 2020) of which, 11 species are known from South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: Ground Velvet Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Dresserus fuscus* Simon, 1876

MORPHOLOGY: Body size: 6–20 mm; males slightly smaller than females. Colour: carapace variable, from red-brown to dark-grey to black; abdomen sometimes spotted; legs dark. Carapace rectangular; high in cephalic region; usually densely clothed with setae; fovea circular and variable in depth; *Dresserus* males have short hornlike structures on anterior edge of carapace; eyes eight, median eyes close together, with lateral eyes wide apart and posterior lateral eyes usually positioned far back on the carapace. Abdomen oval and thickly clothed with setae; cribellum 3-or 4-partite. Legs short; stout and thickly clothed with setae, the tarsi are usually joined to metatarsi by almost rigid joints.

LIFE STYLE: The ground horned velvet spiders are slow moving, sluggish spiders that make retreat webs of bluish-white silk. The capture web consists of shroud-like, loosely woven silk trap-lines extending outwards. They are found in a variety of habitats. Their webs are usually made in dark, sheltered places, e.g. under stones or rocks, crevices or in cracks in the soil. The egg sacs are deposited inside the retreat.

TAXONOMY: The genus has not yet been revised. It is difficult to distinguish between *Dresserus* and *Gandanameno* species as they look very similar and they only differ in the structure of the cribellum and the horns in the males of *Dresserus*. Based on the combination of genetic, morphometric, and spinulation data, Miller et al. 2012 see no evidence that the characters traditionally used to discriminate *Gandanameno* species are valid. They speculate that ontogenetic factors are responsible for the morphological variation in this genus (perhaps juvenile nutrition or post adult moulting). However, they judge that the synonymy of all *Gandanameno* species is premature, particularly in light of the phylogeographic signal suggested by the molecular data.

Dresserus sp., Photo L. Botha

Hornlike tubercles on carapace of male of *Dresserus* Photo ASD

4-partite cribellum of *Dresserus*

GENUS *DRESSERUS* Simon, 1876

KEY TO THE SPECIES OF *DRESSERUS* IN SOUTH AFRICA

- 1. Abdomen with white spots.....5
 - Abdomen without white spots 2

- 2. Abdomen is a dull testaceous3
 - Abdomen more yellowish4

- 3a Abdomen is a dull testaceous brown, covered with short setae (Gauteng)*D. colsoni*
- 3b Abdomen dull testaceous , with moderately long dark setae (Free State).....*D. kannemeyeri*
- 3c Abdomen infuscated testaceous, clothed with black setae (WC).....*D. nigellus*
- 3d Mouse-brown; whole body covered with greyish-black setae (KZN).....*D. obscurus*
- 3e Darker in colour above and below, being of a silky greenish black (EC).....*D. olivaceus*
- 3f Abdomen dull testaceous, and clothed with moderately long dark setae (NC, WC).....*D. schreineri*

- 4a Abdomen pale yellowish, covered with olive-brown setae (NC).....*D. laticeps*
- 4b Abdomen pale yellowish or smoky, clothed with black setae and uniform in colour (NC).....*D. namaquensis*
- 4c Abdomen pale fawn (KZN)..... *D. tripartitus*

- 5a Abdomen speckled with white setae above and spots form lines of white setae at the sides (WC)....*D. angusticeps*
- 5b Abdomen is grey with pale spots; posterior median eyes large and separated from anterior lateral eyes (WC)
.....*D. collinus*

Dresserus angusticeps Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: St Helena Bay Ground Velvet Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Purcell(1904) from St. Helena Bay. The species has been recorded from two coastal localities in the Western Cape (EOO<100 km²; AOO= 8 km²; 84-109 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore it is listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

LIFE STYLE: The species is a ground dweller making retreat-webs and found mainly under stones in the Fynbos biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* St. Helena Bay (-32.77, 18.03); Brand-se-Baai (-31.42, 18.01).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range. The species is threatened by loss of habitat due to farming activities in the St. Helena Bay.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female.

Epigynum after Purcell (1904)

Undescribed male Brand se Baai ASD

Undescribed male palp Brand se Baai ASD

Dresserus collinus Pocock, 1900

COMMON NAME: Table Mountain Ground Velvet Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described by Pocock (1900) from Table Mountain National Park. The species has more recently been sampled from three protected areas (EOO=2 382 km²; AOO=12 km²; 9-266 m a.s.l.). Its status remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range, therefore listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

LIFE STYLE: The species is found in retreat webs, mainly under stones. Sampled from the Fynbos Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* De Hoop Nature Reserve (Potberg) (-34.45, 20.44); Table Mountain National Park (Table Mountain) (-33.82, 18.48); Bontebok National Park (-34.07, 20.45); Napier (-34.46, 19.89).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the following areas: De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009); Bontebok National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020) and Table Mountain National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020). Some more sampling is needed to determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female.

Dresserus collinus female from Napier Photo Kobus Visser

Dresserus collinus female De Hoop Nature Reserve Photo Charles Haddad

Dresserus colsoni Tucker, 1920

COMMON NAME: Common Ground Velvet Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Tucker (1920) from Lydenburg in Mpumalanga. The species is recorded from five provinces including >10 protected areas (EOO=213 998 km²; AOO= 108 km²; 54-1909 m a.s.l.). Although it is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and can be listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species is commonly found in retreat-webs, mainly under stones and sometimes in compost heaps in gardens. Sampled from the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Foord et al. 2011; Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Meyersdal (-26.3, 28.09); Pretoria/Tshwane (-25.74, 28.19); Ezemvelo Nature Reserve (-25.8, 28.77); Bronkhorstspuit (-25.80, 28.74); Carletonville, Farm Elandsfontein (-26.44, 27.45); Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (-27.59, 27.53); Vereeniging (-26.67, 27.92); Irene veldt (-25.89, 28.23). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Mkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.40, 31.39); Ophathe River crossing (-28.52, 31.66). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-24.65, 28.67); Springbok Flats (Tuinplaas) (-24.56, 28.46); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.03, 29.45); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Rust de Winter (-25.19, 28.63); Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (-23.82, 30.16); Pafuri Waller's Camp (-22.424, 30.911). **Mpumalanga:** Barberton (-25.79, 31.04); Groblersdal (Kameeldrift) (-25.16, 29.39); Loskop Research Station (-25.17, 29.4); Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46); Oudestad Experimental Farm (-25.2, 29.2); Verloren Vallei Nature Reserve (-25.53, 30.13). **North West:** Carletonville, Farm Elandsfontein (-26.44, 27.45)

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in >10 protected areas such as: Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003); Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2008); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2009); Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015); Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2015) and Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female (Tucker 1920).

4-partite cribellum Photo ASD

Dresserus colsoni female from Irene Photo Peter Webb

Epigynum after Tucker (1920) Epigynum Photo ASD

Dresserus colsoni undescribed male

Dresserus kannemeyeri Tucker, 1920

COMMON NAME: Kannemeyer's Ground Velvet Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described Tucker (1920), from Smithfield in the Free State. The species has been sampled from several localities in the Free State and Gauteng and occurs in three protected areas: (EOO=75 714 km²; AOO= 36 km²; 1253-1673 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species and due to its wide geographic range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species is commonly found in retreat-webs found under rocks and ground debris, sometimes in compost heaps in gardens. Sampled from the Grassland Biome (Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State:** Bloemfontein (Farm Hopefield) (-29.11, 26.22); Bloemfontein (Farm Deelhoek) (-29.11, 26.22); Fouriesburg Wyndford Guest Farm (-28.70, 28.24); Mpetsane Conservation Estate (-28.92, 27.58); Smithfield (-30.21, 26.53); Erfenis Dam Nature Reserve (-28.50, 26.80). **Gauteng:** Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve (-27.59, 27.53); Pretoria/Tshwane (Rietondale Research Station) (-25.74, 28.19); Nooitgedacht (-25.74, 28.19); Germiston (-26.21, 28.15).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the following areas: Mpetsane Conservation Estate, Erfenis dam Nature Reserve (Haddad et al. 2015) and Suikerbosrand Nature Reserve. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

Dresserus kannemeyeri female from the Free State Photo Peter Webb

Palp after Tucker (1920)

Epigynum after Tucker (1920)

Cribellum after Tucker (1920)

Dresserus kannemeyeri female from the Free State Photo Charles Haddad

Dresserus laticeps Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Northern Cape Ground Velvet Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Northern Cape endemic described by Purcell (1904) from Tsabis. The species was also collected from Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (EOO= 8km²; AOO= 8 km²; 251-1156 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. More sampling is needed to collect the male and determine the species range. Therefore it is listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

LIFE STYLE: The species is rare and found in retreat-webs made under rocks.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape*: Tsabis, 20 m NE Gordonia (-29.26, 17.28); Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (-27.287, 22.486).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2018). Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female.

Epigynum after Purcell (1904).

Dresserus laticeps female from Tswalu KR Photo to Peter Webb

Dresserus namaquensis Purcell, 1908

COMMON NAME: Steinkopf Ground Velvet Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Northern Cape Province endemic described by Purcell (1907) from Steinkopf and Kamaggas. The species was also collected from Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (EOO= 3 291 km²; AOO= 12 km²; 231-870 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range. Therefore it is listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

LIFE STYLE: The species is rare and found in retreat-webs made under rocks in the Succulent Karoo biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape:* Steinkopf (-29.25, 17.73); Kamaggas (-29.75, 17.4); Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (-28.25, 17.17).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female.

Dresserus namaquensis from Rietfontein Farm, Northern Cape Photo J van Eeden

Epigynum after Purcell (1904).

Dresserus nigellus Tucker, 1920

COMMON NAME: Matroosberg Ground Velvet Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Western Cape endemic described BY Tucker (1920) from Matroosberg. The species was also collecting from the Gamkaberg Nature Reserve (EOO < 500 km²; AOO = 8 km²; 980-116 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore it is listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

LIFE STYLE: The species is rare and found in retreat webs made under rocks in the Fynbos biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Western Cape:* Matroosberg (-33.42, 19.84); Gamkaberg Nature Reserve (-33.31, 21.71).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the Gamkaberg Nature Reserve. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female.

Epigynum after Tucker (1920).

Dresserus nigellus female from Gamkaberg NR Photo ASD

Dresserus obscurus Pocock, 1898

COMMON NAME: Natal Ground Velvet Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described in 1898 from Estcourt. Only one additional record from KwaZulu-Natal is known (EOO < 500 km²; AOO = 8 km²; 29-189 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore it is listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

LIFE STYLE: The species is rare and found in retreat-webs made under rocks in the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Haddad et al. 2013; Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal*: Estcourt (-29, 29.87); Richards Bay (15 km N) (-28.78, 32.1).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female.

Epigynum after Pocock (1898).

Dresserus olivaceus Pocock, 1900

COMMON NAME: Grahamstown Ground Velvet Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described in 1900 and known only from the type locality Grahamstown (EOO= 4 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 552 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore it is listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

LIFE STYLE: The species is rare and found in retreat-webs made under rocks in the Thicket Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range. Redescription of type specimen is needed.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female.

Dresserus schreineri Tucker, 1920

COMMON NAME: Hanover Ground Velvet Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 1920 from Hanover. The species is protected in the Karoo National Park (EEO= 8 km²; AOO= 8 km²; 1212-1358 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to determine the species' range. Therefore it is listed as Data Deficient.

LIFE STYLE: The species is rare and found in retreat-webs made under rocks in the Nama Karoo biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape:* Hanover (-30.94, 24.53). *Western Cape:* Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoedman et al. 1999). Some more sampling is needed to determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes.

Palp after Tucker (1920)

***Dresserus tripartitus* Lawrence, 1938**

COMMON NAME: Three cribellum Ground Velvet Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A KwaZulu-Natal endemic described by Lawrence (1938) and known only from the type locality Pietermaritzburg (EOO=4 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 647 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species' range. Therefore it is listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

LIFE STYLE: The species is rare and found in retreat-webs. Sampled from the Savanna Biome

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *KwaZulu-Natal:* Pietermaritzburg (-29.6, 30.38).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Some more sampling is needed to collect the male and to determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female

Epigynum after Lawrence (1938).

Cribellum after Lawrence (1938).

UNDETERMINED SPECIES

***Dresserus* spp.**

Dresserus sp. male from Kapala Game Reserve Photo P. Webb

Dresserus sp. male from Lekgalameetse Nature Reserve Photo P. Webb

GENUS *GANDANAMENO* Lehtinen, 1967

The genus *Gandanameno* is represented by five species, all African endemics (World Spider Catalog (2020)). Only three are known from South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: Tree Velvet Spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Gandanameno spenceri* (Pocock, 1900)

MORPHOLOGY: The bark velvet spiders are large with a velvety appearance. Body size: female 15–25 mm, male smaller in size. Colour: various hues of dark-brown, to greyish-black, abdomen sometimes with small white spots or faint chevron markings; legs dark. Carapace rectangular, cephalic region strongly raised, usually densely clothed with setae, fovea circular but variable in depth; eyes eight, median eyes close together, with lateral eyes wide apart and posterior lateral eyes usually positioned far back on the carapace; abdomen: oval and densely clothed with setae; cribellum: 2-partite; legs: short and stout and thickly clothed with setae, tarsi and metatarsi are usually united by almost rigid joints.

ABUNDANCE: Not very common.

LIFE STYLE: They usually live on bark and build a funnel like retreat with the entrance sheltered under a tarpaulin like, flat signal web. The webbing is bluish white. There are associated with crevices in or under rocks or tree bark in savanna, parks, and gardens. The silken tubes they build have a widened entrance; the tube of an adult female under bark can be up to 1 m long. Also found under tree bark well above the ground. Prey remnants are placed at the bottom of the tube. Juveniles do not feed on their mother's corpse and adult females can produce a number of sequential egg sacs. The eggs are deposited in a sac in the retreat. Males mature in less than one year, females take longer. They grab prey that wanders close to the retreat.

TAXONOMY: Genus not yet revised. It is difficult to distinguish between *Dresserus* and *Gandanameno* species as they look very similar. They only differ in the structure of the cribellum and the presence of horns in the males of *Dresserus*. Based on the combination of genetic, morphometric, and spinulation data, Miller et al. (2012) saw no evidence that the characters traditionally used to discriminate *Gandanameno* species are valid. They speculate that ontogenetic factors are responsible for the morphological variation in this genus (perhaps juvenile nutrition or post adult moulting). However, they judge that the synonymy of all *Gandanameno* species is premature, particularly in light of the phylogeographic signal suggested by the molecular data

Gandanameno retreat from Cedar berg Photo Ant West

Gandanameno sp. VM SANSA

KEY TO THE SPECIES

1. Abdomen with spots.....2
 - Abdomen dull testaceous with short scanty setae; no white rings around dorsal stigmata; species distinguished by lack of spines on under surface of femora, coxae of first leg..... *G. purcelli*
2. Abdomen with white spots; stigmata with white rings around dorsal stigmata; femora of anterior legs is thickly covered with minute sharp spinules.*G. fumosa*
 - Abdomen olive yellow dull lightly mottled with paler spots; spots on the dorsal surface form short lines on the lateral surface; dorsal stigmata white-ringed; smaller than fumosus*G. spenceri*

G. purcelli

G. fumosa

G. spenceri

Gandanameno fumosa (C. L. Koch, 1837)

COMMON NAME: Spotted Velvet Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 1837 as *Eresus fumosus* with type locality only given as “Africa”. The species is recorded from five provinces in South Africa, including five protected areas; (EOO=860 393 km²; AOO= 48 km²; 9-1399 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species and due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least concern.

LIFE STYLE: They usually live on bark and build a funnel-like retreat with the entrance sheltered under a flat, tarpaulin-like signal-web. Sampled from the Fynbos, Savanna, Grassland, Desert and Succulent Karoo biomes (Haddad et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Middelburg (-31.49, 24.99). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (-29.11, 26.22). **Limpopo:** Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Blouberg Nature Reserve ((-22.99, 29.04). **Cape:** Naauwpoort, near Hanover (-31.13, 24.57); Port Nolloth (-29.25, 16.87); Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (-28.25, 17.17); Tswalu Game Reserve (-27.30, 22.44). **Western Cape:** Goukamma Nature Reserve (-34.030, 22.550); Paradise Beach (-34.09, 24.89); Robben Island (-33.80, 18.35); Table Mountain National Park (-34.41, 18.32); Kogelberg Biosphere Reserve (-34.32, 18.96).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the following areas: Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008); Table Mountain National Park (Dippenaar-Scvhoeman 2020); Goukamma Nature Reserve; Tswalu Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2018); Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020) and Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes (C. L. Koch (1837).

Gandanameno fumosa from Kogelberg Photo Willie Steenkamp

Palp after Tucker (1920)

Gandanameno fumosa male Photo Charles Haddad

Epigynum after Tucker (1920)

Habitus after C. L. Koch (1837)

Gandanameno purcelli (Tucker, 1920)

COMMON NAME: Purcell's Velvet Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Tucker (1920) as *Eresus purcelli* from East London. The species is recorded from six provinces, including ten protected areas (EOO= 759 337 km²; AOO=60 km²; 9-1212 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species. Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and is thus listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species builds a retreat-web under stones and ground debris or sometimes under loose bark. Sampled from the Grassland, Savanna, Thicket, Fynbos and Indian Ocean Coastal Belt biomes (Haddad et al. 2013; Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** East London (-33.01, 27.9); Grahamstown (Farm Gretna) (-33.3, 26.52); Addo Elephant National Park (-33.32, 25.72); **Gauteng:** Kloofendal Nature Reserve (-26.14, 27.86). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Ophathe River (-28.395, 31.394). **Limpopo:** Kruger National Park (-22.93, 31.02). **Northern Cape:** Oorlogskloof Nature Reserve (-31.45, 19.1). **Western Cape:** Kogelberg Biosphere Reserve (-34.32, 18.96); Swartberg Nature Reserve (Gamkaskloof) (-33.36, 21.69); Karoo National Park, Stalshoogte (-32.28, 22.46); Kirstenbosch National Botanical Garden (-33.982, 18.433); Robben Island (-33.80, 18.35); Stellenbosch (-33.93, 18.85); Table Mountain National Park (-33.82, 18.48).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the ten protected areas Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1999); Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003); Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005); Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015) and Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2020). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known only from the female Tucker 1920).

Epigynum after Tucker (1920)

Gandanameno purcelli female Photo Vida vd Walt

Gandanameno spenceri (Pocock, 1900)

COMMON NAME: Spencer's Velvet Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1900 as *Eresus spenceri* from Port Elizabeth. The species is recorded also from Zimbabwe. In South Africa it is known from five provinces, including six protected areas (EOO=731 161 km²; AOO= 72 km²; 7-1711 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species. Due to the wide geographical range, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species is commonly found under stones and ground debris, as well as under bark. Sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland and Savanna biomes Haddad et al. 2013; Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Cradock (-32.16, 25.61); Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.43); Port Elizabeth (-33.95, 25.61); Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Tsolwana Nature Reserve (-32.171, 26.50). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Cedara Forest Reserve (-30.16, 29.32). **North West:** Brits (Swartberg) (-25.62, 27.77). **North-ern Cape:** Hanover (-30.94, 24.53); Kamaggas (-29.75, 17.4); Kimberley (Hillcrest) (-28.76, 24.74); Steinkopf (-29.25, 17.73). **Western Cape:** Swartberg Nature Reserve (Gamkaskloof) (-33.36, 21.69); De Hoop Nature Reserve (Potberg) (-34.45, 20.44); Prince Albert (Tierberg) (-33.13, 22.25); Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36, 21.69); Gamkaberg Nature Reserve (-33.31, 21.71); Robben Island (-33.80, 18.35)

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in several protected areas such as: De Hoop Nature Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2009); Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005) and Mountain Zebra National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2006). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Not revised. Known from both sexes. (Pocock 1900)

Gandanameno spenceri female Photo John Hill

Palp after Lehtinen (1967)

Epigynum after Lehtinen (1967)

Female epigynum Photo ASD

GENUS *PARADONEA* Lawrence, 1968

Paradonea is represented by five African endemic species (WSC 2020)

COMMON NAMES: Decorated Velvet Spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Paradonea striatipes* Lawrence, 1968

MORPHOLOGY: Distinct sexual dimorphism occurs in size and colour. The females can be various hues of dark brown, yellowish brown or grey, with small dark abdominal spots while the males have distinct colour patterns on the carapace and abdomen. Females usually have grey legs, and the legs of males are sometimes banded. Their rectangular carapace is high and densely clothed with short setae. The cribellum is bipartite, the legs short and stout and densely setose. The cephalic region of the carapace is well raised above the thoracic region and the oval abdomen is densely clothed with setae. Anterior legs are longer than posterior legs. Anterior lateral eyes are placed on distinct tubercles.

ABUNDANCE: Rare

LIFE STYLE: Little is known about the behaviour of the decorated velvet spiders. These are slow-moving, sluggish spiders that live on the soil surface. They make retreat webs with a funnel-shaped retreat consisting of arrays of radiating threads covered with hackled bands of cribellate silk.

TAXONOMY: Revised by Miller et al. (2012)

Paradonea parva

Paradonea presleyi

Paradonea variegata

Paradonea striatipes

Paradonea splendens

Paradonea parva (Tucker, 1920)

COMMON NAME: Decorated Velvet Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1920 as *Adonea parva* from the junction of the Crocodile and Marico Rivers in Limpopo. The species is known from three southern African countries. In South Africa, the species has been recorded from four provinces, including four protected areas (EOO= 317 041 km²; AOO= 64 km²; 116-1394 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species. Although the species is presently known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range and can be listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: They build silken tubes under stones or under shrubs. Sometimes, spiders build a round web approximately 10 cm in diameter that may be covered with sand and herbal debris. Sampled from the Grassland and Savanna biomes, often by pitfall trapping Haddad et al. 2013; Foord et al. 2011).

DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, Botswana and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: Free State: National Botanical Gardens (-29.05, 26.21). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.90,29.04); Junction Crocodile & Marico Rivers (-24.19,26.87); Mara (-23.04, 29.66); Vhembe Biosphere Mara Research Station (-23.138, 29.551). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park Napi (-25.37, 31.51); Kruger National Park Randspuit (-25.28, 31.64); Kruger National Park Sabiepoort (-25.19, 32.20); Kruger National Park Satara (-24.617, 31.883); Kruger National Park Skukuza-Malelane (-25.011, 31.464); Kruger National Park Skukuza-Malelane (-25.316, 31.566); Kruger National Park Skukuza-Malelane (C03U) (-25.204,31.577). **Northern Cape:** Kuruman (Dithakong Tribal Land) (-27.46, 23.43); Benfontein Nature Reserve (-28.73, 24.76); Hopetown (4 km W) (-29.62, 24.06). **North West:** Junction Crocodile & Marico Rivers (-25.19, 26.87).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in four protected areas such as Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019) and Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Miller et al. (2012) Known only from the male.

Paradonea parva male Photo Les Oates

Male palp Photo ASD

Paradonea parva male Photo ASD

Paradonea parva male eye pattern

Paradonea presleyi Miller, Griswold, Scharff, Rezac, Szuts & Marhabaie, 2012

COMMON NAME: Presley's Velvet Spider

NATIONAL STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described from Zimbabwe in 2012. In South Africa, the species is recorded from two provinces, including five protected areas (EOO= 8 589 km²; AOO= 32 km²; 285-1341 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species. Although known only from one sex it has a wide geographical range in southern Africa, and is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: They build a silken tube-like nest under stones or under shrubs. Males have been sampled from pitfall traps in the Savanna biome.

DISTRIBUTION: Zimbabwe, South Africa

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Luvhondo Nature Reserve (-23.038, 29.442); Mara (-23.04, 29.66); Vhembe Biosphere Ben Lavin Nature Reserve (-23.133, 29.926); Vhembe Biosphere Blouberg Nature Reserve North (-22.96, 29.086). **Mpumalanga:** Kruger National Park (-24.98, 31.58).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the following areas: Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2020); Blouberg Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2019); Ben Lavin Nature Reserve and Luvhondo Nature Reserve. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Known from only the male.

Paradonea presleyi male Photo Charles Haddad

Palp after Miller et al. (2012).

Paradonea presleyi male from Tshipise Photo John Wilkinson

Paradonea splendens (Lawrence, 1936)

COMMON NAME: Splendid Velvet Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described by Lawrence (1936) as *Adonea splendens* from Gemsbok Pan. In South Africa, the species is recorded from two provinces (EOO= 10 665 km²; AOO= 12 km²; 1102-1345 m a.s.l.). The species is possibly under collected. Too little is known about the location, habitat and threats of this taxon for an assessment to be made. Placement of the species is also problematic; it is therefore listed as Data Deficient for Taxonomic reasons.

LIFE STYLE: The species is a ground-dweller. They build silken tubes under stones or under shrubs. Sampled from the Grassland and Savanna biomes (Haddad et al. 2013; Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Gauteng:** Sunnyside (-25.75, 28.21). **Northern Cape:** Gemsbokpan (-29.47, 23.58); Benfontein Nature Reserve (-28.748, 25.056).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the Benfontein Nature Reserve. More sampling needed.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Miller et al. (2012) Known only from the male.

Male palp after Muller et al. (2012)

Paradonea splendens male after Muller et al. (2012)

Carapace after Muller et al. (2012)

Paradonea striatipes Lawrence, 1968

COMMON NAME: Black and White Velvet Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Lawrence (1968) from Namibia. The species also occurs in South Africa and is presently recorded from the Northern Cape (EOO= 8 km²; AOO= 8 km²; 1238-1326 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species. Due to its wide southern Africa geographical range, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species is a ground-dweller. They build silken tube-like nests under stones or under shrubs. Sampled from the Savanna Biome (Haddad et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Northern Cape:* Kathu (-27.69, 23.06); Dithakong Tribal Land 65 km NE Kuruman (-27.46,23.43); Brandewynfontein Farm, Pixley Ka Seme District (-30.552, 24.999).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Need more sampling to collect the female.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Miller et al. (2012). Known only from the male.

Male after Muller et al. (2012)

Male palp after Muller et al. (2012)

Paradonea striatipes male from Brandewynfontein
Photo: J. van Eden

Paradonea variegata (Purcell, 1904)

COMMON NAME: Spotted Velvet Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic described by Purcell (1904) as *Adonea variegata* from Naroep in the Northern Cape. The species is known from three Southern African countries. In South Africa, it is recorded from two provinces, including two protected areas (EOO= 160 394 km²; AOO= 60 km²; 56-1405 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species. Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: Known from savanna and semiarid desert. They build silken tube like nests under stones or under shrubs. Sometimes, spiders build a round web approximately 10 cm in diameter that may be covered with sand and herbal debris. Juveniles feed on their mother's corpse before dispersing. Adults appear around December, juveniles disperse in October (Miller et al 2012). Sampled from the Savanna, Nama Karoo, Succulent Karoo and Fynbos biomes (Haddad et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, Botswana, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Northern Cape:** Calvinia (-31.46, 19.77); Kamaggas (-29.75, 17.4); Namies (-29.29, 19.2); Nariiep (Naroep) (-30.77, 17.64); Pella (-29.03, 19.13); Steinkopf (-29.25, 17.73); Breekkierie Dunes (-30.12, 21.55); Namaqua National Park (-30.05, 17.35). **Western Cape:** Cederberg (Dwarsriver) (-32.16, 18.89); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Matjiesfontein (-33.24, 20.58); Touwsriver (-33.44, 21.18); Worcester (-33.64, 19.47); Nieuwoudtville (Bokkeveld Mts) (-31.37, 19.11).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the following areas: Namaqua National Park and National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1999). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by (Miller et al. 2012). Known from both sexes.

Epigynum after Purcell (1904)

Palp after Miller et al. (2012)

Paradonea variegata female and male from Pella
Photo Stefan Nesper

Paradonea variegata female Photo Les Oates

Paradonea variegata male Photo Stefan Nesper

UNDETERMINED

***Paradonea* sp.**

Paradonea sp. female from Lephahlale Peter Webb

GENUS *SEOTHYRA* Purcell, 1903

Seothyra is an African genus represented by 13 species and five are reported from South Africa.

COMMON NAMES: Common Buckspoor Spider

TYPE SPECIES: *Seothyra schreineri* Purcell, 1903

MORPHOLOGY: Body-size female medium-sized; distinct sexual dimorphism in shape colour and size; male slightly smaller. Colour various hues of dark brown, yellowish-brown to grey; abdomen in both sexes with distinct patterns formed by white, orange or red setae on a dark background; legs similar in colour to body; males more brightly coloured. Carapace rectangular; high, thickly clothed with dense setae; fovea circular but variable in depth; eyes 8 with median eyes close together; lateral eyes wide apart and posterior lateral eyes usually positioned far back on carapace. Abdomen round-oval and clothed with short setae; spinnerets modified – only anterior pair well developed.

LIFE STYLE: Buckspoor spiders are ground dwellers and are commonly found in more arid regions. They construct burrow retreat-webs consisting of a burrow lined with silk. The entrance is covered with a lobed silk flap that serves as a signal-web. The upper part of the silk flap is covered with sand and resembles a hoofprint (buckspoor) in the sand, hence the common name. Juveniles and females live in these burrows. During the mating season the males are active during the day, running on the soil surface in search of females. With their decorative patterns they mimic *Camponotus* ants. The egg-sacs are deposited in the burrow. Some Bushmen from the Kalahari regard them as venomous, and smear the spider's body on arrowheads when out hunting.

TAXONOMY: Revised by Dippenaar-Schoeman (1991).

Seothyra fasciata female from Gysdorp Photo Les Oates

Seothyra longipedata male Photo L. Oates

Seothyra fasciata buck spoor Photo Les Oates

Seothyra fasciata Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Gordonia Buckspeer Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic described in 1904 from Gordonia in the Northern Cape. It is known from three Southern African countries. In South Africa, the species is recorded from two provinces including six protected areas (Eoo= 391 769 km²; AOO= 48 km²; 540-1197 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species. Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFESTYLE: They construct burrow retreat-webs consisting of a burrow lined with silk. The entrance is covered with a lobed silk flap that serves as a signal web. The upper part of the silk flap is covered with sand and resembles a hoofprint (spoor of a buck) in the sand. Sampled from the Succulent Karoo, Savanna and Nama Karoo biomes (Haddad et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, Botswana, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Limpopo:** Messina/Mussina (Farm Onseigegron) (-22.34, 30.03); Waterpoort (Farm Rochdale) (-22.54; 29.41); Mosdene Nature Reserve (-24.52; 28.7); Waterpoort Farm Rochdale (-22.54, 29.41); Vhembe Biosphere Goro Game Ranch (-22.939,29.428). **Northern Cape:** Augrabies National Park (-28.66, 20.42); Benfontein Game Reserve (-28.82, 24.82); Breekkierie Dunes (-30.12, 21.55); Gordonia (-28.7, 20.96); Kalagadi Transfontier Park (Twee Rivieren) (-26.43, 20.26); Steinkopf (-29.25; 17.73); Upington, 19.2 km W (-28.4, 21.24); Upington, 8 km NW (-28.45, 21.24); Witsand Nature Reserve (-34.39; 20.85).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in five protected areas: No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Dippenaar-Schoeman (1991). Known from both sexes.

Seothyra fasciata female from Tswalu Photo Peter Webb

Epigyne and palp after Dippenaar-Schoeman (1991)

Seothyra fasciata male Kalahari Trails Photo N Larsen

Carapace and abdomen after Dippenaar-Schoeman (1991)

Buckspeer web

Seothyra longipedata Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1991

Common name: Northern Cape Buckspoor Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A Southern African endemic described in 1991 from Namibia. The species is also recorded in South Africa from two provinces and two protected areas (EOO=92 473 km²; AOO= 20 km²; 78-920 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species. Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: They construct burrow retreat-webs consisting of a burrow lined with silk. The entrance is covered with a lobed silk flap that serves as a signal web. The upper part of the silk flap is covered with sand and resembles a hoofprint (spoor of a buck) in the sand. Males wander in search of mates. Sampled from the Desert, Fynbos and Savanna biomes (Haddad et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Northern Cape:** Upington (Farm Grootdrink) (-28.6, 21.7); Upington Farm Eselsfontein (-28.62, 21.68); Gordonia (-28.70, 20.96); Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park (3 km SW of Claim Peak) (-28.25; 17.17). **Western Cape:** Cederberg Wilderness Area (-32.16, 18.89).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the following areas: Richtersveld Transfrontier National Park and the Cederberg Wilderness Areas No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Dippenaar-Schoeman (1991). Known from both sexes.

Seothyra longipedata Photo E. Pietersen

Epigynum after Dippenaar-

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Seothyra longipedata male Photo L. Oates

Palp and abdomen after Dippenaar-Schoeman (1991)

Seothyra perelegans Simon, 1906

COMMON NAME: Bothaville Buckspoor Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A South African endemic described in 1906 from Bothaville. The species has a restricted distribution (EEO= 8 km²; AOO= 8 km²; 815-1291 m a.s.l.) and has only been sampled from two provinces. The status of the species remains obscure. More sampling is needed, to collect the female and more accurately determine the species' range. Therefore it is listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

LIFE STYLE: The species makes burrow retreat-webs consisting of a burrow lined with silk. The males run around in search of mates. Sampled from the Grassland and Nama Karoo biomes (Haddad et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Willowmore (-33.3, 23.5). *Free State:* Bothaville (-27.38, 26.62).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Dippenaar-Schoeman (1991). Known only from the male.

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Abdomen after
Dippenaar-Schoeman (1991)

Seothyra schreineri Purcell, 1903

COMMON NAME: Schreiner's Buckspoor Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1903 from Hanover in the Northern Cape. The species has been recorded from both Namibia and South Africa. In South Africa, it is known from three provinces, including three protected (EOO= 152 542 km² AOO= 40 km²; 581-1402 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species, and due to its wide geographical range it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: They construct burrow retreat webs consisting of a burrow lined with silk. The entrance is covered with a lobed silk flap that serves as a signal web. The upper part of the silk flap is covered with sand and resembles a hoofprint (spoor of a buck) in the sand. The males run around in search of a mate. Sampled from the Desert, Nama and Succulent Karoo biomes.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Free State** Luckhoff (-29.73, 24.77). **Northern Cape:** Hanover (-30.94, 24.53); Hopetown (4 km W) (-29.62, 24.06); Poortjiesfontein (-30.97, 24.45); Onderste Narries (-28.55, 19.83); Augrabies National Park (-28.66, 20.42); Witsand Nature Reserve (-28.36, 23.05). **Western Cape:** Beaufort West (Farm Eerste Water) (-32.69, 22.96); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Prince Albert (-33.22, 22.03).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the following areas: Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1999), Witsand Nature Reserve and Augrabies National Park. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Dippenaar-Schoeman (1991). Known from both sexes.

Epigynum after Dip-

Palp and abdomen after Dippenaar-Schoeman (1991)

Seothyra schreineri female Photo ASD

Seothyra schreineri male Photo ASD

Seothyra semicoccinea Simon, 1906

COMMON NAME: Willowmore Buckspoor Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: DDT

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An Eastern Cape endemic described in 1906 and only known from the type locality, Willowmore, Eastern Cape (EOO= 4 km²; AOO= 4 km²; 815 m a.s.l.). The status of the species remains obscure. Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species' range. Therefore, it is listed as Data Deficient for taxonomic reasons.

LIFE STYLE: The species is a ground-dweller and makes a retreat-web. Males run around in search of mates. Sampled from the Nama Karoo Biome.

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Eastern Cape:* Willowmore (-33.3, 23.5).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Some more sampling is needed to collect the female and to determine the species range.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Dippenaar-Schoeman (1991). Known from only the male.

Palp and abdomen after Dippenaar-Schoeman (1991)

GENUS *STEGODYPHUS* Simon, 1873

Stegodyphus is known from 20 species of which 12 are known from Africa and Madagascar World Spider Catalog (2020).

COMMON NAMES: Stegodyphus Velvet Spider/ Community Nest Spiders

TYPE SPECIES: *Stegodyphus lineatus* (Latreille, 1817)

MORPHOLOGY: Body size female medium-sized; males smaller with distinct sexual dimorphism in colour. Colour various hues of dark brown, yellowish brown to grey, with patterns; male with abdomen sometimes with distinct patterns formed by white, orange or red setae; legs sometimes banded. Carapace rectangular; high; thickly clothed with setae; fovea circular but variable in depth; 8 eyes with median eyes close together, lateral eyes wide apart and posterior lateral eyes usually positioned far back on carapace; abdomen round-oval and clothed with dense setae; legs short and stout, and thickly clothed with setae.

LIFE STYLE: They have different life styles with two species known as community nest spiders that are social spiders living together in large retreats made of cribellate silk and debris. The retreat consists of numerous tunnels and chambers, and is attached to structures above ground level – usually branches. Several sheet-like webs, consisting of parallel threads crisscrossed with cribellate silk forming a ladder-like structure, are used to catch prey. All inhabitants work together to catch prey and to repair the web. Mating takes place in the retreat, where the egg-sacs are also deposited.

TAXONOMY: Revised by Kraus & Kraus (1989).

Stegodyphus feeding Photo Aart Louw

Stegodyphus community nest Photo Dai Herbert

Stegodyphus africanus (Blackwall, 1866)

COMMON NAME: African Stegodyphus Velvet Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Blackwall (1866) as *Eresus africanus* from French Equatorial Africa. It has a wide distribution throughout Africa. In Southern Africa, it is known from five countries including South Africa and Swaziland. In South Africa, the species is recorded from four provinces and three protected areas (EOO= 684 108 km²; AOO=48 km²; 140-1551 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species. Due to its wide geographical range, it listed as being of Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species is a plant-dweller and makes a retreat-web on vegetation. Sampled from the Succulent Karoo, Grassland, Savanna and Nama Karoo biomes (Haddad et al. 2013; Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Angola, Cameroon, DRC, Mozambique, Namibia, Swaziland, Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **KwaZulu-Natal:** Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.87, 32.24); Underberg, Sangwana (-29.79, 29.5). **Limpopo:** Blouberg Nature Reserve (-22.99, 29.04); Kruger National Park: Punda Milia (-22.68, 31.01), between Shingwedzi and Letaba (-23.12, 31.43), Mooketsi (-23.59, 30.08); Soutpansberg (-31.04, 20.04); Vaalwater (-24.29; 28.11). **Mpumalanga:** Shiluvane (-24.03, 30.27). **Northern Cape:** Colesberg (-30.73, 25.11); Steinkopf (-29.25, 17.73); Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (-27.287, 22.486). **North West:** Barberspan (-26.62, 25.58).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the following areas: Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006); Blouberg Nature Reserve (Muelwa et al. 2010; Foord et al. 2019) and Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003); Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2018). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Kraus & Kraus (1989). Known from both sexes.

Stegodyphus africanus female Photo O. Kraus

Palp after Kraus & Kraus (1989)

Stegodyphus africanus female Photo Anka Eichhoff

Epigynum after Kraus & Kraus (1989)

Stegodyphus bicolor (O. P. Cambridge, 1869)

COMMON NAME: Bicolor Stegodyphus Velvet Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described from Namibia as *Eresus bicolor* in 1869. The species is known from two African countries. In South Africa, it is recorded from the Northern Cape and protected in the Augrabies National Park (EOO= 1 918 km²; AOO= 12 km²; 33-720 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species, and due to its wide global range, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species makes retreat-webs and lives solitarily in a nest made with yellow-orange silk in vegetation. Sampled from the Desert and Succulent Karoo biomes .

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Namibia, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Northern Cape:** Augrabies National Park (-28.66, 20.42); Riemvasmaak (-28.45, 20.31); Naroep (-28.98, 18.58).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the Augrabies National Park. No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Kraus & Kraus (1989). Known from both sexes.

Epigynum after Kraus & Kraus (1989)

Palp after Kraus & Kraus (1989)

Epigynum after Kraus & Kraus (1989)

Stegodyphus dumicola Pocock, 1898

COMMON NAME: Dumicola Community Nest Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described by Pock (1898) from Estcourt in KwaZulu-Natal. The species is known from seven African countries. In the Atlas Region known from Swaziland and South Africa. In South Africa, the species has been recorded from all nine provinces and is protected in more than 10 protected areas (EOO= 1 528 630 km²; AOO= 236 km²; 7-1758 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species. Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species makes retreat-webs and lives in community nests in trees. Sampled from the all of the biomes except the Desert Biome (Haddad et al. 2013; Foord et al. 2011). The species was also sampled in citrus orchards (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2013).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Angola, Botswana, Mozambique, Namibia, Swaziland, Zimbabwe and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Grahamstown (-33.3, 26.52); Grahamstown (Goodwins Kloof) (-33.9, 29.47); Grahamstown (Gretna, 6 km SW) (-33.3, 26.52); Jeffrey's Bay (-34.06, 24.91); Middelburg (-23.9, 29.47); Middelrift (-32.82, 26.98); Pearston (-32.59, 25.15); Somerset East (-32.73, 25.6). **Free State:** Kroonstad (-27.65, 27.24); Mpetsane Conservation Estate (near Clocolan) (-28.8, 27.65); Vredefort (-27, 27.37); Wepener (-23.9, 29.47). **Gauteng:** Roodepoort (-23.9, 29.47), Hekpoort (-23.9, 29.47); Modderfontein (-23.9, 29.47); Pretoria/Tshwane: University of Pretoria, Exp. Farm (-25.73, 28.17), Gezina (-25.72, 28.21), Wonderboom, Saltpan (-25.68, 28.2); Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-25.64, 28.36); Roodepoort National Botanical Garden (-23.9, 29.47). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Estcourt (-29, 29.87); Hluhluwe (Ubizane Ranch) (-28.02, 32.28); Ladysmith (Klip River) (-28.55, 29.76); Mhlopheni Nature Reserve (-28.96, 30.39); Mkuzi Game Reserve (-27.63, 32.25); Mseleni (-27.19, 32.32); Ndumo Nature Reserve (-26.93, 32.24); Pongola (Farm Vergeval) (-27.35, 31.61); Spioenkop Dam Nature Reserve (-28.55, 29.76). **Limpopo:** Hoedspruit, 5 km S (-24.34, 30.93); Kruger National Park: Shingwedzi-Babalala (-22.93, 31.02), between Shingwedzi and Letaba (-22.93, 31.02), Olifants camp (-24.02, 31.75), Skukuza (-22.93, 31.03); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Pietersburg/Polokwane (-23.89, 29.46); Polokwane Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47); Waterberg (-24.33, 28.33); Makalali Private Game Reserve (-24.16, 30.69). **Mpumalanga:** Barberton (-25.79, 31.04); Hectorspruit (Farm Lekkerdraai) (-25.43, 31.68); Lydenburg (-25.09, 30.46); Kruger National Park: Pumbe

Palp after Kraus & Kraus (1989)

Epigynum after Kraus & Kraus (1989)

Stegodyphus dumicola females feeding together Photo Philip Fouche

Stegodyphus dumicola Addo Photo Linda Wiese

Stegodyphus dumicola male Photo L. Oates

Stegodyphus dumicola continued

Picket (-24.22, 31.93), Skukuza (-25.0, 31.97). North West: Mafikeng (-25.82, 25.63); Molopo Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47). **Northern Cape:** Augrabies National Park (-28.58, 20.35); Dibeng (-27.59, 22.87); Kgalagadi Transfrontier Park (Urikaruus Camp) (-25.78, 20.39); Kimberley (-28.73, 24.76); Nariep (-30.77, 17.64); Nieuwoudtville (-31.37, 19.11); Upington (-28.45, 21.24). Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (-27.287, 22.486). **Western Cape:** Cape Town (-33.91, 18.42); Cederberg Camp (Kromrivier) (-32.16, 18.89); Karoo National Park (-32.28, 22.46); Table Mountain National Park (Table Mountain) (-33.82, 18.48).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in >10 protected areas such as Roo-deplaatdam Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1989); Karoo National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 1999); Makalali Private Game Reserve (Whitmore et al. 2001); Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003); Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008); Polokwane Nature Reserve (Dippenaar et al. 2008); Lhuvhondo Nature Reserve (Foord et al. 2008); Nylsvley Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2009); Tswalu Kalahari Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2018). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Kraus & Kraus (1989). Known from both sexes.

Stegodyphus dumicola specimens feeding together Photo C. Haddad

Stegodyphus dumicola females Photo J. Leeming

Stegodyphus mimosarum Pavesi, 1883

COMMON NAME: Bushy Leg Community Nest Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described by Pavesi (1883). The species has a wide distribution throughout Africa. In South Africa, it has been recorded from eight provinces and seven protected areas (EOO=784 730 km²; AOO= 100 km²; 17-1467 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species. Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species makes retreat-webs and lives in community nests in trees. Sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland, Indian Ocean Coastal Belt and Savanna biomes (Haddad et al. 2013; Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Widely throughout Africa and Madagascar.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Middelburg (-23.9, 29.47); Mzimhlava River mouth, Lusikisiki (-31.37, 29.57). **Free State:** Bloemfontein (Farm Deelhoek) (-23.9, 29.47). **Gauteng:** Roodeplaatdam Nature Reserve (-23.9, 29.47). **KwaZulu-Natal:** Durban (-29.85, 31.01); Hluhluwe Nature Reserve (Ubizane) (-28.02, 32.28); Mkuzi Nature Reserve (-27.6, 32.02); Mseleni (-27.19S, 32.32E); Ndumo Game Reserve (-26.93, 32.24); Pinetown (-29.81, 30.85); Richmond (-29.86, 30.26); Spioenkop Dam Nature Reserve (-28.55, 29.76); Mkhuzi Game Reserve (-27.6, 32.02); Ophathe Game Reserve (-28.52, 31.66); Pinetown (-29.81, 30.85); Verulam (-29.62, 31.06). **Limpopo:** 5 km S of Hoedspruit (-24.34,30.93); Kruger National Park: Punda Milia (-22.68, 31.01), Springbok Flats (Tuinplaas), (-24.56, 28.46); Maastroom (Farm Al-te-Ver) (-23.9, 29.47); Sandrivierspoort, Waterberg (-24.33, 28.33); Mica (-24.18, 30.82). **Mpumalanga:** Barberton (-25.79, 31.04); Kruger National Park (Skukuza Camp) (-25.00, 31.97). **Northern Cape:** Boegoeberg Dam (-28.5, 26.8). **Western Cape:** Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36,21.69); Bontebok National Park (-34.07, 20.45).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in >10 protected areas. Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003); Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005); Ndumo Game Reserve (Haddad et al. 2006); Ophathe Game Reserve (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman 2015). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Kraus & Kraus (1989). Known from both sexes

Stegodyphus mimosarum Photo Otto Kraus

Palp after Kraus & Kraus (1989)

Stegodyphus mimosarum male Photo P. Webb

Epigynum after Kraus & Kraus (1989)

Abdomen after Kraus & Kraus (1989)

Stegodyphus sabulosus Tullgren, 1910

COMMON NAME: Dark Stegodyphus Velvet Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: An African endemic described from Tanzania in 1910. Only known from four African countries. In South Africa, the species is recorded only from the Kruger National Park, Nwambiya Pan in the Limpopo Province (EOO < 500 km²; AOO = 8 km²; 319-418 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species. Due to its wide geographical range, it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species makes retreat webs on vegetation. Sampled from the Savanna Biome (Haddad et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Kenya, Swaziland, Tanzania and South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: *Limpopo:* Kruger National Park (Nwambiya Pan) (-22.93, 31.02).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the Kruger National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Leroy 2003). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Kraus & Kraus (1989). Only known from the female.

Abdomen after Kraus & Kraus (1989)

Stegodyphus sabulosus female Photo C. Haddad

Stegodyphus tentoriicola Purcell, 1904

COMMON NAME: Pale Stegodyphus Velvet Spider

CONSERVATION STATUS: LC

NATIONAL RATIONALE: A southern African endemic described in 1904 from Hanover in the Northern Cape. The species is known from three African countries. In South Africa, it is recorded from six provinces and protected in five protected areas (EEO= 645 308 km²; AOO= 60 km²; 54-1722 m a.s.l.). There are no significant threats to the species, and due to its wide geographical range it is listed as Least Concern.

LIFE STYLE: The species makes retreat-webs on vegetation and has been sampled from grass heads. Sampled from the Fynbos, Grassland and Savanna biomes (Haddad et al. 2013; Foord et al. 2011).

GLOBAL DISTRIBUTION: Botswana, Namibia, South Africa.

DISTRIBUTION IN SOUTH AFRICA: **Eastern Cape:** Herschel (-30.62, 27.16); Mountain Zebra National Park (-32.24, 25.54); Middelburg (-29.73, 27.03); Twee Rivieren (-31.48, 26.03); Swartkops (-33.87, 25.63). **Free State:** Wepener (-29.73, 27.03). **Gauteng:** Krugersdorp / Mogale (-26.14; 27.86); Centurion (-25.9; 27.61). **Limpopo:** Makapansgat (-24.15, 29.18); Makalali Private Game Reserve (-24.16, 30.69). **Northern Cape:** Eierfontein (-31.06, 24.4); Vlagkop, Hanover (-30.94, 24.53); Kalagadi Transfontier Park (Twee Rivieren) (-26.43, 20.26); Witsand Nature Reserve (-26.02; 25.5); **Western Cape:** Karoo National Park (-26.08; 28.17); Swartberg Nature Reserve (-33.36; 21.69).

CONSERVATION MEASURES: Protected in the following areas: Mountain Zebra National Park, Kalagadi Transfontier Park (Twee Rivieren), Karoo National Park, Swartberg Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman et al. 2005); Witsand Nature Reserve; Makalali Private Game Reserve (Whitmore et al. 2001); Mountain Zebra National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman 2006). No conservation actions are recommended.

TAXONOMIC NOTES: Revised by Kraus & Kraus (1989). Known from both sexes.

Stegodyphus tentoriicola female Photo Otto Kraus

Epigynum after Kraus & Kraus (1989)

Stegodyphus tentoriicola female Photo Anka Eichhoff

Palp and abdomen after Kraus & Kraus (1989)

Stegodyphus tentoriicola female Photo Les Oates

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